

SECURITY AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT: PREDICTORS OF THEIR LOYALTY IN THE LODGING INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the interplay of security measures and employee engagement is vital for enhancing employee loyalty in the lodging industry. This study examines the influence of security and engagement on employee loyalty within Bukidnon's lodging establishments. Security is categorized into management, operational, and physical security, while employee loyalty includes both behavioral and attitudinal loyalty. A descriptive correlational research design was used to analyze data from 120 employees, employing a survey questionnaire based on the previous studies: Torralba and Ylagan (2021), Anichiti et al. (2021), and Ahla and Osac (2014) for hotel security, Narciso and Narciso (2022) for engagement, Dede and Sazkaya (2018) and Kolomiets (2016) for employee loyalty. Regression analysis assessed the influence of lodging security and engagement on employee loyalty. Findings reveal that employees generally rate security measures positively across various dimensions, including management, operational, and physical security. They also demonstrate very high levels of engagement in maintaining a secure environment, and behavioral and attitudinal loyalty. The analysis indicates that employees' positive assessment of security and engagement significantly influences their loyalty. Specifically, management and physical security have the strongest positive influence on employee loyalty, while operational security and employee engagement have less impact. The study recommends enhancing management, operational, and physical security and implementing initiatives to foster engagement to create a safer and more committed workforce. By implementing these recommendations, lodging establishments can create a more secure environment, enhancing employee loyalty. This contributes to the sustained success and competitiveness of Bukidnon's lodging industry.

Keywords: *Employee Engagement, Lodging Industry, Loyalty, Security*

INTRODUCTION

In the lodging industry, fostering employee loyalty is essential and is linked to two key factors: security and the level of engagement among employees. When the establishment implements effective security measures, it ensures everyone's safety and cultivates a positive workplace atmosphere. Employees who feel safe, engaged, and valued tend to be happier in their jobs, leading to better performance and directly impacting the service guests receive. Creating a work environment where security and engagement go hand in hand builds a strong team and fosters employee loyalty.

Ensuring safety among employees fosters a positive workplace atmosphere, enhancing their sense of security, engagement, and commitment to their work. Clifton (2023) noted that intensified security concerns must be addressed by proactively initiating and implementing safety and security planning as important parts of their operations. This proactive approach is essential for stimulating overall security measures and ensuring the well-being of both employees and guests, thereby promoting loyalty to the organization. Supporting this concept, Mazzetti and Schaufeli (2022) suggest that when employees feel secure and engaged, they exhibit greater job satisfaction and performance, resulting in enhanced service quality for guests. This emphasizes the critical connection between security and engagement, fostering a collaborative work environment that cultivates strong relationships among team members and nurtures long-term employee loyalty within the lodging industry.

There are several security issues encountered by the lodging industry within global, national, and even local contexts, that shed light on the critical importance of the conduct of this study. This is demonstrated by two recent high-profile security incidents: the Ivory Coast hotel hostage crisis 2023 of Ivory Coast, West Africa, in which terrorists kidnapped numerous guests before their capture by local police forces (BBC NEWS, 2016), and the Davao City, Philippines, bombing event in 2022 that attacked a hotel, caused multiple injuries, and heightened regional security concerns (BBC NEWS, 2016). In the local context of this study, incidents ranging from theft and vandalism to terrorism and cyber-attacks highlight the need for vigilance and effective security measures. These events serve as reminders of the challenges lodging industry faces at all levels (Visnov, 2024).

Numerous studies have examined the connection between security and employee engagement and their effect on loyalty in the lodging sector (Agaku et al., 2020). Nonetheless, a substantial gap exists in the literature, especially when it comes to investigating the connection between several security facets—operational, physical, and managerial security—and employee engagement. However, very little is known about how these variables affect behavioral and attitudinal loyalty in the specific setting of Bukidnon's lodging sector. To respond to this gap, this study will look into how, in this particular regional context, extensive security and employee engagement measures influence loyalty.

Framework

This study assumed that lodging establishments with strong security protocols—which include management, operational, and physical security—as well as a focus on employee engagement, would exhibit significantly higher levels of employee loyalty. Furthermore, by ensuring a secure and engaging work environment, these establishments are likely to foster trust and commitment among their employees, leading to increased employee loyalty. This assumption is anchored on the Theory of Social Exchange by George Homans (1961).

Social Exchange Theory suggests that when people interact, they aim to gain mutual benefits. In the context of the lodging industry, there's an implicit agreement between the establishment and its employees. When an establishment puts effort into strengthening its security and fostering positive employee engagement, employees perceive this as a distinct advantage. This sense of security not only makes employees feel safer but also instills a greater desire to work, thereby enhancing their loyalty towards the organization. This sense of security not only makes employees feel safer but also instills a greater desire to work, thereby enhancing their loyalty towards the establishment.

The studies of Abdul Majid and Samsudin (2017) have underscored that strengthening security measures in the lodging sector increases employees' sense of safety and fosters loyalty to the organization. Employees gain from this sense of stability, which fosters commitment and loyalty. The mutually reinforcing nature of these exchanges, based on SET principles, provides the foundation for comprehending how security and employee engagement work together to foster organizational loyalty in the hotel sector. The investigation of how these categories interact and affect employee attitudes and behaviors—which in turn shape the performance and atmosphere of the organization—is guided by this theoretical framework. The findings from Srinivasan's study add to the ongoing discussions about security in lodging establishments, confirming that addressing security concerns is essential for keeping employees loyal. These studies highlight that both physical and psychological security play a big role in making employees feel loyal.

Within the hospitality industry, lodging security has a big impact on employee loyalty. Employees are immediately affected by the security measures in their everyday work environment in addition to being in charge of putting them into place. According to research, when employees feel valued and engaged at work, they are more likely to feel safe and secure, which raises job satisfaction and loyalty levels. Successful security procedures may provide employees confidence and trust by assuring them that the organization values their safety. According to Morch (2022), one important thing is that security should cover more than just protecting things like equipment. Now, employees see security measures as essential not only for keeping physical things safe but also for ensuring their own safety and well-being at work.

Several security measures substantially influence employee loyalty, such as management, operational, and physical security. Management security has a significant influence on employee loyalty. Elphick (2024) highlights that control protection is a key and vital part of the hospitality industry. Lodging establishments pay a lot of attention to

dealing with safety issues. Control safety is important for employee safety and property security, creating a secure and welcoming atmosphere that improves the overall work experience. Moreover, it shields the establishment's valuable assets, reducing financial risks and disruptions in operations.

Operational security is another dimension influencing employee commitment and loyalty. Conrad (2011) describes it as the application of controls to reduce threats and vulnerabilities, including the security of confidential information. This intricate area includes various procedures, guidelines, and methods to keep guests, employees, and property safe. Roar (2023) provides an essential insight into efficiently managing and implementing operational security in the lodging industry. Finally, physical security represents another crucial facet of security. Devoteam (2023) highlights the critical role of physical security as a safeguard for employees, facilities, and assets against real-world threats, whether internal or external. Cobb (2022) found that by implementing physical security measures, lodging establishments protect their employees and assets, from unauthorized access or physical actions that could result in damage or substantial losses, serving as a preventive measure against security breaches and threats in the physical space.

Employee engagement is another dynamic variable affecting employee loyalty. In security, employee engagement refers to the enthusiasm, devotion, and commitment of employees in maintaining a safe environment. This includes adherence to security procedures, alertness to risks, and participation in security awareness programs. According to Smith (2023), employee engagement encompasses not only the mental and emotional commitment of workers to their jobs but also their readiness to make contributions toward the organization's overall security objectives. Employees that are actively involved in security are more likely to display actions that improve security protocols, like promptly reporting suspicious activity, adhering to established protocols, and cooperating with security staff members. For this reason, employee engagement in security is essential to guaranteeing the effectiveness of security protocols and protecting both the safety of guests and employees.

The dependent variable, employee loyalty, refers to the steadfast commitment of hotel employees to their workplace. Employee loyalty is essential for maintaining an engaged and effective workforce, which influences service quality and guest satisfaction. Recent studies (Henry, 2023) indicate that employment satisfaction, organizational culture, and leadership effectiveness significantly influence employee loyalty. Workers who feel supported, respected, and valued by their employer are more likely to develop strong loyalty. Research by Cornell (2019) shows that employee loyalty can be divided into two key aspects: attitudinal loyalty and behavioral loyalty. It is crucial to understand how security and employee engagement contribute to both attitudinal and behavioral loyalty in the lodging industry.

Training employees is crucial for improving their behavior, particularly in security. Attitudinal loyalty, focusing on emotional commitment, highlights the role of trust in fostering positive attitudes toward security measures (Halbusi et al., 2023). Garcia et al. (2022) explore how job satisfaction relates to attitudinal loyalty.

Figure 1, on the next page, illustrates the intricate relationship among the variables examined in this study. The independent variable consists of two components: the first one includes the level of security, encompassing dimensions such as management security, operational security, and physical security. The second independent variable is employee engagement. Meanwhile, the dependent variable involves employee loyalty, covering both behavioral loyalty and attitudinal loyalty. The central argument suggested in this study is that employee loyalty is significantly influenced by the level of security and employee engagement.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

Research Objective

This study aimed to determine the influence of security and employee engagement on employee loyalty among lodging establishments in the province of Bukidnon

METHODOLOGY

The participants of this study were employees from five DOT-accredited lodging establishments in Bukidnon regardless of contract, with a minimum of one year of experience were considered eligible to participate. There were 120 participants who responded to the study. Participants were chosen based on their availability and willingness to join the study. The researcher employed accessible population sampling.

Smith & Jones (2018) defined accessible population sampling as the inclusion of individuals or subjects who are readily available and easily accessible for research purposes. The selected hospitality establishments were chosen from the Department of Tourism's (DOT) official list.

The selected lodging establishments were situated in Bukidnon and are varied in size, ranging from small to medium-sized establishments accommodating between 20 to 100 guests. Annually, they cater to approximately 200 to 500 guests, depending on the season. The establishments, categorized as business and resort hotels, have been operational since the early 2000s. They offer a wide range of amenities and facilities, including accommodations, business and meeting facilities, recreation and leisure facilities, entertainment options, kids' clubs, and family amenities, as well as 24-hour front desk and security services, among others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarizes the assessment of hotel security. The data show that hotel security is generally rated as "Very Good," with an overall mean rating of 4.30. This indicates a positive perception of hotel security among the participants. A stable and secure environment is facilitated by the hotels' strong administrative protocols, well-defined security rules, regular staff training, and proactive risk management. The average ratings for various aspects of lodging security, such as management security (M=4.41), operational security (M=4.24), and physical security (M=4.25), also reflect a positive perception among the participants. These results are consistent with research conducted by Bertulino (2022), highlighting the importance of management, operational, and physical security as an investment that not only protects employees but also enhances their well-being, productivity, and loyalty to the organization. The variation in assessments underscores the critical necessity of consistently evaluating and adapting hotel security measures to maintain a safe and secure workplace environment for employees.

Table 1.
Summary Table of Assessment of Hotel Security

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Management Security	4.41	Very Good	0.57
Operational Security	4.24	Very Good	0.61
Physical Security	4.25	Very Good	0.56
Overall Assessment	4.30	Very Good	0.54

Management security received the highest mean rating of 4.41, indicating employees' strong confidence in the lodging's management practices and their effectiveness in ensuring security. This high rating suggests that the lodging operations have established security policies and procedures on security staff training, guest information management, emergency response planning, access control systems, reporting security incidents, and updating security equipment. However, the lower rating for operational security (M=4.24), although still rated as very good, indicates areas for

improvement, such as enhancing staff training programs, implementing advanced security technologies, and streamlining operational procedures for increased efficiency and effectiveness. Lodging security is crucial for providing peace of mind and reducing theft risks, particularly for valuable items like jewelry and electronics. Kumar (2023) emphasizes the importance of protecting lodging employees, guests, and assets. A proper security system is essential for safeguarding staff, guests, and physical resources, including equipment, buildings, gardens, and guest belongings.

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' assessment of employee engagement. The data show that employees assessed their engagement as very high, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.67. This reflects a very high level of perceived effectiveness in responding to employee engagement through the provision of positive workplace factors such as supportive management, good working conditions, effective communication, and opportunities for professional growth. This overall assessment is supported by the frequency and percentage distribution indicated in the table, where the majority of employees rated engagement as "Very High" (70.0%). These factors show that employees in the selected hotels in Bukidnon generally feel highly engaged in their work.

Table 2.

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Level of Engagement in the Selected Hotels in Bukidnon

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	84	70.0
3.51-4.50	High	36	30.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	0	0.0
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.0
Total		120	100.0
Overall Mean		4.67	
Interpretation		Very High	
SD		0.28	

However, it is also noteworthy that 30% of the participants rated their engagement as "High." While this designation still reflects a positive assessment of employees' engagement, it indicates that there is room for improvement. These factors show that employees in the selected hotels in Bukidnon generally feel highly engaged in their work. This high level of engagement could be attributed to various positive workplace factors such as supportive management, good working conditions, effective communication, and opportunities for professional growth. Although the high rating represents a favorable evaluation, specific areas like communication and feedback need improvement. Engaged employees contribute positively to productivity and a positive work environment. Security training is crucial for maintaining safety for both employees and guests. Management should focus on improving communication channels, encouraging participation, and providing feedback opportunities to enhance security measures and ensure a safe

working environment. Overall, the results show that employees have a high opinion of the security measures and engagement practices in place. This positive perception underscores the importance of continuing to develop and refine these areas to maintain and further enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty. By addressing the identified areas for improvement, hotels can foster an even more secure and engaging environment for their staff, leading to sustained success and competitiveness in the industry.

Table 3 presents a summary of employee loyalty across two dimensions: behavioral and attitudinal loyalty. With an overall mean of 4.13 and a "High" interpretation, this emphasizes a strong demonstration of employees' loyalty. These findings are particularly remarkable in the hotel industry, where maintaining high levels of employee loyalty is important for delivering consistent service quality and enhancing satisfaction. These findings underscore a positive workplace culture where employees maintain favorable attitudes towards their work, colleagues, and supervisors, fostering a cohesive and supportive environment. Overall, these results highlight the high level of employee loyalty demonstrated by hotel employees.

Table 3.
Summary Table of Employee Loyalty

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Behavioral Loyalty	4.22	High	0.54
Attitudinal Loyalty	4.03	High	0.56
Overall Employee Loyalty	4.13	High	0.52

Among the two dimensions, behavioral loyalty shows the highest mean score of $M=4.22$. This is associated with employees demonstrating consistent and committed behaviors in their roles within the hotel establishment. This implies that when employees feel valued, engaged, and empowered, they are more likely to demonstrate dedication and consistency in their work. As supported by Henry (2023), loyal employees are more engaged, productive, and committed to achieving organizational goals.

On the other hand, attitudinal loyalty, which receives a mean score of 4.03 and is also considered "High," is defined as employees' emotional attachment, commitment, and alignment with the goals, values, and objectives of the hotel organization. This shows that employees encompass positive attitudes, beliefs, and feelings towards their work, colleagues, supervisors, and the overall hotel environment, which promotes a cohesive and positive workplace culture.

These findings indicate that the observed high levels of employee loyalty, both behavioral and attitudinal, are crucial for the hotel industry's success. Employees are likely to exhibit consistent and committed behaviors in their roles, contributing to the delivery of consistent service quality and heightened guest satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of nurturing and maintaining employee loyalty as a key factor in achieving operational excellence and a competitive advantage within the hotel industry (Ogbeide & Isokpan, 2020).

Table 4 presents the regression analysis which provides valuable insights into the participants' assessment of hotel security and engagement on their loyalty. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=33.22$ $p = .000$), indicating that the null hypothesis can be rejected. Participants who gave high ratings to the hotel security also tend to have higher loyalty.

As for their engagement, even though this variable alone does not significantly influence their loyalty, it contributes to the variability of their loyalty when combined with their assessment of hotel security. This underscores the interconnected nature of factors influencing employee loyalty.

Among the specific indicators, physical security has the highest influence on employee loyalty, indicating that for every unit increase in their assessment of physical security, there is a corresponding 0.280 increase in their loyalty ($B=0.280$, $t=2.39$, $p=0.019$). This indicates that employees place significant importance on physical security measures when evaluating their loyalty to the hotel. As attested by Agaku et al. (2020), the singular power of words underscores the paramount importance of safety and security in the hospitality industry, particularly for employees and guests. To attract, retain, and remain competitive, hoteliers must prioritize creating a safe and conducive environment for both guests and employees. This factor also significantly contributes to fostering loyalty among employees.

Table 4.

Regression Table on the Influence of Participants' Assessment of Hotel Security and Engagement on their Loyalty

	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients	Std. Error	Coefficients		
	B		Beta		
(Constant)	1.06	.217		4.89	.000
Management Security	-.037	.077	-.041	-.486	.628
Operational Security	.057	.084	.071	.681	.498
Physical Security	.233	.097	.268	2.41*	.018
Engagement	.216	.084	.265	2.58*	.011
Model Summary					
R = .732 R ² = .536 Adjusted R ² = .520 F = 33.22** p = .000					

**significant at 0.01 level *significant at 0.05 level

Furthermore, the findings suggest that while operational security and engagement individually do not significantly impact loyalty, they still play a role in contributing to the overall variability in loyalty when combined with other factors. This highlights the complex nature of employee loyalty, which is influenced by various aspects of their experience at the hotel. These results align with existing literature on the subject which emphasizes the importance of security measures in shaping employee perceptions and loyalty. Studies have shown that lack of adequate security measures can negatively impact their loyalty and overall satisfaction. Given that these actions may increase employee loyalty, hotels may want to prioritize fortifying their operational security procedures and improving their

physical security infrastructure.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study reveals valuable insights into the effect of employees' assessments of hotel security and engagement on their loyalty in the lodging industry. Among the specific indicators, physical security has the highest influence on their loyalty. The findings support the assumption that employees in hotel establishments with high security measures and high engagement levels are more likely to feel happy and loyal to their establishment.

Additionally, the findings provide empirical evidence for the application of Social Exchange Theory (SET) in the context of this study. SET posits that when hotel employees receive positive security measures and heightened employee engagement, they are more likely to exhibit increased loyalty and commitment to the organization. In this study, positive treatment is exemplified through factors security, employee engagement, and loyalty.

Further analysis of the findings emphasizes that management and physical security have the strongest positive influence on employee loyalty. This suggests that lodging establishments should enhance existing programs supporting security measures, such as security awareness training, leadership development workshops, customer service training, and technical skills enhancement, to promote a safe and supportive work environment. While employee engagement and operational security are significant factors in overall loyalty, this study suggests they may not be perceived as primary drivers of loyalty by the employees. Instead, the provision of operational and security measures alone may not suffice to instill a deep sense of commitment to the organization.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that proper protocols were observed in the gathering of data. First, approval from the The school's Research and Ethics Committee was sought. Once the ethical clearance was granted, permission from the management of the five identified hotel establishments was sought. Then, participants were asked to sign a consent form before the study commenced. Upon approval, the researcher physically administered the survey questionnaire to the participants during their breaks or off-duty hours. Additionally, health protocols such as wearing masks and physical distancing were strictly observed. Participants in this study were thoroughly informed about the purpose and details of the research, ensuring transparency throughout. They were given the option to refrain from answering questions or discontinue their participation if they felt uncomfortable or offended. Research ethics aims to protect people's rights in research and ensure fairness. Researchers should be transparent, and honest, and avoid exploiting participants when seeking ethical approval (Nchasi, 2021). As a gesture of appreciation for their involvement, participants received tokens of gratitude. It was

emphasized that all data collected during this research would be treated with complete confidentiality.

Furthermore, participants were assured that their privacy and confidentiality were safeguarded through adequate measures. The study's results did not include any personal identifiers, preserving the anonymity of individuals. Participants also were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study for personal reasons, and their test results became part of Lourdes College. Any release of such information occurred only with the explicit approval of the Department Chairperson or College Dean, reinforcing the commitment to the ethical handling of participant data.

To safeguard the privacy of participants and comply with the Data Privacy Act, the researcher implemented the Belmont Report specifically on respect for persons, beneficiaries, and justice. Access to the research data was restricted to the researcher and authorized personnel only, ensuring that participants' information remained confidential throughout the study and beyond. Furthermore, participants received tokens as a gesture of appreciation for their valuable contribution to the research.

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